

Interaction of metronidazole with amino acids and their thermodynamics

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Interactions of the drug metronidazole with amino acids viz. tryptophan, tyrosine, phenylalanine and alanine have been studied and the thermodynamic parameters calculated. The drug has been found to interact with amino acids in water. The interaction may not be simple charge-transfer interactions; other interactions like hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interaction and dipole-dipole interaction are equally possible. The stability of the complexes indicates fairly stable complex formation.

Most of the compounds of medicinal interest commonly known as drugs undergo different interactions in the biological system. However, the main reaction is the physicochemical interaction between the drug and functionally important molecule in the living organism known as receptor, a portion of the bacteria or microbe of the respective etiological agent^{1,2}.

Amoebiasis is a typical disease and widely prevalent in India. A large number of compounds with varying structures and properties are known as amoebicides and therefore amoebicides can be classified as non-specific drug where certain physicochemical properties are of importance for drug activities^{1,3}. Metronidazole (MDZ) is one such important antifungal and antiprotozoal agent which is widely used in the treatment of trichomoniasis and probably one of the most effective drug against intestinal amoebiasis and giardia lamblia. A concentration of 1–2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ or even less is sufficient to destroy *E. histolytica*, the etiological agent for amoebiasis⁴.

Amino acids which are constituents of proteins are expected to interact reversibly with the drug molecule. Though it may be difficult to understand the nature of interactions of drug with simple amino acids, it may be possible to suggest the probable binding sites from the relative strengths of the drug-amino acid complexes.

This led us to determine the interaction of amino acids like *l*-alanine, *l*-phenylalanine, *l*-tyrosine and *l*-tryptophan with the well known antiamoebic drug metronidazole in aqueous solution spectrophotometrically at different temperatures. The results are reported in the present communication.

Results and discussion

Metronidazole (MDZ) is fairly soluble in water. It

absorbs strongly in the uv region. The maxima near 230 nm appears to be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions whereas those near 320 nm appear to be due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The addition of MDZ to amino acids changes the absorption maxima and absorbance of the solutions appreciably indicating interaction or complex formation. A typical example is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Absorption vs wavelength(nm) : (a) 0.4×10^{-4} (M) MDZ in water, (b) 0.4×10^{-4} (M) tryptophan in water, (c) 0.4×10^{-4} (M) MDZ + 0.4×10^{-4} (M) tryptophan in water.

The equilibrium constants of the complexes were determined assuming the composition of the complexes to be 1 : 1 but they were not verified by Job's method of continuous variation or by other methods. The correctness of the assumption had been found to be true from the consistency of the results obtained from the derived equation based on 1 : 1 complex formation.

The equilibrium constant K for the reaction,

can be written as

$$K = \frac{[AD]\gamma_{AD}}{[A][D]\gamma_A\gamma_D} \quad (2)$$

where $[A]$, $[D]$ and $[AD]$ are the equilibrium concentrations of A, D and AD respectively and γ are the activity coefficients respectively. Here A is the amino acid and D = MDZ.

In view of low concentrations of reactants and products and uncharged nature of the molecules $\gamma_{AD}/\gamma_A\gamma_D$ can be reasonably regarded as unity.

The expression (2) can be written as

$$K = \frac{x}{(c_1 - x)(c_2 - x)} \quad (3)$$

where x is the equilibrium concentration of the complex AD, c_1 and c_2 are the initial concentrations of A and D respectively.

Since all the components A (except alanine), D and AD absorb strongly in the UV region, usual expressions like Benesi-Hildebrand⁵ equation is not applicable. Moreover, uncertainties exist in the values of K using one of the components like D in large excess. The accurate values are usually obtained⁶ when $[A]_0 \approx [D]_0$.

The equation utilised⁷ is

$$\frac{c_1}{(d-d_1-d_2)} = \frac{1}{(\varepsilon-\varepsilon_1-\varepsilon_2)} + \frac{1}{(c_2-x)(\varepsilon-\varepsilon_1-\varepsilon_2)K} \quad (4)$$

where ε_1 , ε_2 and ε are the extinction coefficients and d_1 , d_2 and d are molar absorptivity of A, D and AD respectively.

$$D_1 = \varepsilon_1 c_1 l, d_2 = \varepsilon_2 c_2 l \text{ and} \\ D = \varepsilon x l + \varepsilon_1 (c_1 - x) + \varepsilon_2 (c_2 - x) l \quad (l = \text{path length} = 1 \text{ cm}) \quad (5)$$

and

$$x = \frac{d-d_1-d_2}{(\varepsilon-\varepsilon_1-\varepsilon_2)} \quad (6)$$

An iterative procedure starting initially when $x=0$ was used to evaluate $(\varepsilon-\varepsilon_1-\varepsilon_2)$ and K . Usually two to three iterations were sufficient to get consistent set of K and ε values. The K and ε values of the complexes are presented in Table 2.

ΔG° , the standard Gibb's energy changes were calcu-

lated from the relation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = -2.303 RT \log K \quad (7)$$

Assuming ΔH° (enthalpy of the reaction) to remain constant in the temperature range studied (293–313 K), ΔH° has been obtained from the slope of the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$. The linearity of the plot indicated the validity of the assumptions.

Table 1. Absorption maxima of the amino acids, MDZ and their complexes

Drug	λ_{\max} (nm)	Amino acid	λ_{\max} (nm)	Complex (drug + amino acid) λ_{\max} (nm)
MDZ	320, 230	Alanine	–	318–320 225
		Phenylalanine	270, 222	273 220
		Tyrosine	275, 222–223	320 225
		Tryptophan	280, 220	289–290 222

ΔS° (entropy of the reaction) have been obtained from the relation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (8)$$

The values of $\log K$, ΔG°_{298} , ΔH°_{298} and ΔS°_{298} have been recorded in the Table 2.

The results as given in Table 2 show that the drug interacts fairly strongly with amino acid in the order tryptophan > phenylalanine > tyrosine > alanine. The reactions are instantaneous and the solutions can be kept for several hours. However, the sequence of the equilibrium constants cannot be correlated with either pK_1 , or pK_2 of the amino acids. It is to be noted that under the conditions of the experiment i.e. pH = 6 (near the isoelectric points of the amino acid), the amino acids are present mainly as neutral acid or zwitter ions or slightly excess of negatively charged acids may result. But no correlation of the equilibrium constants with isoelectric pH of the amino acids can be made.

It is difficult to ascertain the nature of the complexes. Complex formation is usually inferred from the observation of a new band usually in the long wavelength region (red shift) for CT complexes and in the short wavelength region (blue shift) for H-bonded complexes. The band is conspicuous when only the complex or one of the components and complex absorb in the spectral region of interest. But when both the components and the complex absorb in the same region it is difficult to identify the band and the spectrum of the complex is deceptive due to the superimposition of bands⁸. In the present investigation though the components and the complex absorbed in the same region the absorption maxima of complexes are different; a blue shift with respect to the drug and red shift with respect to

Table 2. Thermodynamic and other constants for complexes of MDZ with amino acids in aqueous medium

Amino acid	Temp. (°K)	K_{AD} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	ϵ_{AD} dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ × 10 ⁴	log K_{AD}	ΔH_{298}° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG_{298}° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_{298}° J deg K ⁻¹
Alanine	293	221.3	0.697	2.34	-23.09	-12.95	-34.02
	298	188.4		2.27			
	303	162.2		2.21			
	308	141.3		2.15			
	313	119.5		2.07			
Phenylalanine	293	399.6	1.524	2.60	-24.27	-14.13	-33.0
	298	388.8		2.53			
	303	281.8		2.45			
	308	245.5		2.39			
	313	211.5		2.32			
Tyrosine	293	279.50	1.544	2.45	-28.36	-13.63	-49.39
	298	245.50		2.39			
	303	199.50		2.30			
	308	177.80		2.25			
	313	141.25		2.15			
Tryptophan	293	501.25	1.597	2.70	-35.04	-14.88	-67.63
	298	405.30		2.60			
	303	325.20		2.51			
	308	255.40		2.40			
	313	196.00		2.29			

amino acids are observed. Complex formation as well as spectral changes etc. are invariably the result of molecular interactions of varied nature^{8,9} i.e. CT complex as well as H-bonding.

The interaction between MDZ and amino acid is spontaneous and exothermic in character and the reactions, as expected are accompanied with decrease in entropy values due to association of drug and amino acids. But this leads to the increase in ΔG_{298}° (less negative) values. The enthalpy values range from -35 kJ mol⁻¹ to -23 kJ mol⁻¹. The enthalpy changes of the complexes and the entropy decrease are in the order : tryptophan > tyrosine > phenylalanine > alanine.

Experimental

Metronidazole was crystallised from 50% aqueous alcoholic solution and dried and its purity was tested from m.p. determination. Metronidazole was obtained as off-white crystals fairly soluble in water. Amino acids from G.R., E. Merck or B.D.H. were used without purification. Triple-distilled water from all-glass distilling set was used for preparing the solutions.

MDZ and amino acids (except alanine) absorb strongly

in the uv region. The absorption maxima of the amino acids, MDZ and their complexes are presented in Table 1.

For the determination of the association constants, the amino acids and drugs were kept in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature for an hour and different concentrations of the reactants were mixed usually in the ratio 1 : 1. The mixed solution and the blank solutions were kept at the desired temperature to attain equilibrium. The absorptivity values were noted using a thermostated cell compartment controlled at different temperatures. The measurements were made at five different temperatures namely 293, 298, 303, 308 and 313 K.

The measurements were made using a UV-visible spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan, model UV 2201 with a thermostatic attachment.

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